

SOCIAL- PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SELF- CONCEPTION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE

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Annotation : *The image created by imagining a person himself , his behavior characteristics, his position in society is called "I" image, and its adequacy and closeness to reality is one of the criteria of personality perfection.*

Introduction : *The socio-psychological importance of the image of "I" is that it is one of the important factors of personal education and upbringing. From this point of view, education can be defined as the process of formation of a person's ideas about himself and his qualities. Therefore, the more clearly and correctly each person knows and imagines himself, the less likely he is to act against the norms of society, that is, he is educated.*

Books Analysis And Methodology . The process of self- awareness, assessment of existing qualities is often difficult for a concrete person, that is, human nature is such that it is true to the norms of that society. he tries not to understand the undesirable qualities, to "hide" them, even such ideas and knowledge are pushed into the unconscious (according to the theory of the Austrian scientist Z. Freud). This is not a deliberate act, it is a unique defense mechanism of each individual. Such a protective mechanism often protects a person from various bad complications and emotional experiences. But it should be emphasized that the external environment surrounding that person, others and their attitude play a big role in the positive or negative image of "I". A person looks at others and imagines himself as if he sees himself in a mirror. This process is called reflection in psychology. Its essence is to form and revive the image of oneself through the image of people similar to oneself. Reflection is a process involving the mind of the owner of the image of "I". For example, you met an acquaintance on the street. You are constantly telling him about your achievements and training. But you did not pay attention to the fact that he was in a hurry somewhere. You will know this from the fact that he is impatiently listening to you, his imagination is somewhere else, and thus you will feel that you have become "softer, more delicious" at the same time. The next time you meet this friend, avoid making the same mistake as before and say, "Buddy, are you in a hurry?" you ask. This is

the result of earlier reflection. That is, standing in the place of the interlocutor and looking at yourself ("how do I look to him?") is a reflection.

A person's self-image and self-concept are age- and sex-specific. For example, extreme curiosity about oneself, the desire to know and understand who one is, develops especially during adolescence. The sense of "adulthood" that appears in this period determines not only the relationship between girls and boys, but also their relationships with others. The good and positive image of "I" in girls depends more on the ability of this image to embody feminine qualities, the presence of feminine qualities in itself, while the image in boys is more based on the criteria of physical perfection. depends on how compatible it is. That's why the low height, weak muscles and the image of "I" built on this basis in boys cause a number of negative impressions. In girls, the image of "I" is perceived meaningfully, depending on the presence or absence of external beauty, elegance, manners, and a number of other feminine qualities. Even in girls, excess weight or some skin rashes or similar physiological defects cause strong negative emotions, but beautiful clothes, jewelry or a specific hair style are considered as factors that overcome these defects.

Based on the image of "I", a system of self-evaluations is formed in a person, and this system can be different according to the image. Self-esteem can vary depending on various qualities and experiences of a person, and the achievements based on this experience. That is, if the same work increases in terms of achievement, it may decrease under the influence of another - on the contrary. Although this assessment actually depends on the real relationship of others to the person, it is actually formed depending on the criteria in the system of the person's consciousness, that is, how much he himself subjectively values these relationships. For example, if the positive attitude of one subject teacher towards the child, his constant letters increase his self-esteem, the negative attitude of another teacher may not lower this assessment. That is, this assessment depends more on the individual, and it is subjective in nature.

Self-assessment can be not only realistic (adequate), correct, but also extremely low or high.

Low self-esteem is often caused by excessive demands placed on the person by others, inability to meet them, constant objections, failures in work, study, and dealings. can be formed. Such a teenager or an adult is always depressed, tries to stay away from others, is in a mood of insecurity in his own strength and abilities, and gradually a number of negative qualities and behaviors appear in the person.

leads to Even such a situation can cause suicidal actions, i.e. suicide, the psychology of striving to "escape" from reality.

Too high self-esteem does not have a good effect on a person's behavior. Because it is also formed due to the artificial exaggeration of personal achievements or qualities by others, inappropriate praise, trying to avoid various difficulties. The psychological condition that appears in such a situation is called the "inadequacy effect", and as a result of it, even when a person is defeated or feels helpless or uneducated, he believes that it is caused by others and convinces himself of this. (for example, excuses such as "he destroyed it", "if so-and-so was not there" will increase). That is, no matter what happens, it is not the person who is to blame, but the people around them, circumstances, and fate. More and more, people start talking about such people with such adjectives as "down-to-earth", "arrogant", "self-centered". Therefore, self-assessment should be realistic, adequate and correct.

A realistic assessment is a product of reasonable and reasonable assessments of those around a person - parents, close relatives, pedagogues and coaches, neighbors and loved ones, realistic and sincere relationships, and a person has an impartial acceptance of these relationships from early youth. will be taught to do, correct if necessary in time. In this case, the role of reference group, a group of people considered exemplary for a person, is great. Because we don't listen to everyone's opinions and evaluations in our daily life, there are such people for us, whose simple reprimands, advice, even the reprimands given by the school are of great importance. Such a reference group can be real (for example, parents, teachers, mentors, close friends), or unrealistic, imaginary (book characters, favorite actors, ideal). Therefore, if it is necessary to exert appropriate influence or pressure on people in youth education or in a real community, it is of great educational importance to determine their standard, reference group.

Thus , self-esteem is a purely social phenomenon, and its meaning and essence depends on the norms of the society surrounding the individual, the values accepted and respected in this society. Self-esteem, formed as a result of large social groups playing the role of a standard, is a high level of self-esteem. For example, in the conditions of independence, the minds of the youth of our country are being nurtured in the minds of our national values, patriotism, loyalty to the ideology of justice and independence . And this is the foundation and important formative mechanism of that higher self-awareness.

Therefore, self-evaluation is an important criterion of self-education. The factors and mechanisms of self-education include:

- communication with oneself (as the perception of oneself as a concrete object of education and the organization of communication with oneself);
- self-assurance (subordination to positive norms of behavior by believing in one's capabilities, strength and will);
- self-command (the quality of being able to hold oneself in tight and extreme situations and encourage oneself to the right path);
- self-influence or autosuggestion (formation of favorable assumptions based on social norms);
- internal discipline is an important criterion of self-control, the necessary quality to systematically correct and control all one's actions at all times and everywhere.

So, depending on what qualities a person has, the objectivity of his evaluations, a person can control himself by communicating with himself according to the table. That is why there are such people in life. For example , communication in the family circle or among peers serves as a basis for the development of the child's "I". If a child experiences a lot of discrimination or neglect in the family and among peers, there is a possibility that the child's self-esteem will decrease. These are the facts that show that that internal dialogue is different for everyone.

REFERENCES

1. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S., & Boxodirjon o'g'li, V. A. (2022). XORIJ PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 1(12), 39-47.
2. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O'RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 176-182.
3. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(2), 1-3.
4. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 99-105.
5. Ботирова, Н. (2020). Обучающие возможности тестовых технологий.

Профессиональное образование и общество, (3), 68-71.

6. Ботирова, Н. Д. (2019). Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников. Гуманитарный трактат, (61), 4-6.

7. Ботирова, Н. Д. Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников development of productive thinking of younger schoolboys. Журнал выпускается ежемесячно, публикует статьи по гуманитарным наукам. Подробнее на, 4.

8. Ботирова, Н. Д., & Алимджонова, М. Ю. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК БОШЛАНГИЧ СИНФ ЎЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРИНИ ЭВРИСТИК ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ТАШКИЛИЙ ОМИЛЛАРИ. Scientific progress, 3(4), 519-524.

9. Botirova Nasiba Djurabayevna INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS . Eastern European Scientific Journal Germany. 128 – 132 p. <http://www.auris-verlag.de>

10. Alimjanova, M. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF FORMATION OF RESPONSIBILITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF NATIONAL VALUES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 914-917.

11. Alimjonova, M. Y. (2021). The role of the national values in the history of pedagogical education. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(3), 1040-1044.

12. Alimjanova, M. (2021). ABOUT GENDER STEREOTYPES. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL), 2(06), 72-76.

13. Janabergenova, A. J. (2018). Organization and Forms of Students' Independent Work on Higher Mathematics at Pedagogical University. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (2).

14. Janabergenova, A. J. (2021). Setting Goals on Smart Techniques and Affecting Student Motivation. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 9333-9336.

15. Askarova, D. (2022). FORMATION OF CREATIVITY AND

BOOKREADERS QUALITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION.

Science and innovation, 1(B8), 1039-1044.

16. Askarova, D. I. (2022). The Role Of Folk Pedagogy In The Development Of Creativity Of Students Of Higher Educational Institutions. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(02), 89-96.

17. Dilafruz, A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarda Va Oilada Gender Xususiyatlarni Shakllantirish Omillari. *Innovation In The Modern Education System*, 2(18), 183-189.

18. Askarova, D. I. (2022). USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN DEVELOPING CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(10), 92-97.

19. Askarova, D. I., & Jabborova, M. K. (2022). The Introduction Of Gender Issues In Preschool Education On The Example Of Folk Pedagogy. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(05), 81-87.

20. Nurmamatovna, K. S. (2021). The object of pragmatics—the basic of progmatological approach. *Thematics Journal Of Social Sciences*, 7(5).

21. Hakimov, M. X., & Shokirova, H. N. (2021). Personal dexterity options. *Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 789-797.

22. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). Educational Methods in Teaching the Russian Language. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 260-263.

23. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF LISTENING SKILLS IN LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 138-145.

24. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). MECHANISMS OF EFFECTIVE TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING INNOVATIVE METHODS. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 11, 132-135.

25. E. Najmiddinov, A. Rasujonov, & J. Rahimov (2022). FARG‘ONA VODIYSI SUV HAVZALARIDAGI BALIQLAR GELMINTLARI. Science and innovation, 1 (D8), 145-151. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335759
26. Najmiddinov, Eldor , Rasuljonov, Adhamjon, & Rahimov, Javohir (2022). FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2 (10), 1049-1054.
27. E. Najmiddinov (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА “ИХТИОЛОГИЯ ВА ГИДРОБИОЛОГИЯ” СОҶАЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ. Science and innovation, 1 (D8), 152-160. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335800
28. E. Najmiddinov (2022). TABIATNING MAKTABGACHA TA’LIM YOSHIDAGI BOLALARNI BARKAMOL AVLOD BO’LIB SHAKLLANISHIDAGI AHAMIYATI. Science and innovation, 1 (B8), 149-154. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7336353
29. Юлдашев, Э., & Нажмиддинов, Э. (2013). БРАКОНИДЫ (Hymenoptera, Braconidae) РОДА ROGAS NEES ФАУНЫ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ. In Биоразнообразие и рациональное использование природных ресурсов (pp. 134-136).
30. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., Кучбоев, А. Э., Мухаммадиев, М. А., & Соатов, Б. Б. (2021). Эколого-морфологические характеристики нематод рода Rhabdochona-паразитов обыкновенной маринки. Теория и практика борьбы с паразитарными болезнями, (22), 387-393.
31. Kuchbuev, A. E., Najmidinov, E. K., Mukhamediev, M. A., Karimova, R. R., & Yildiz, K. (2021). Morphological and ecological features of some nematodes of the genus Rhabdochona in marinka obtained from Fergana Valley, Uzbekistan. Journal of Parasitic Diseases, 45(4), 1084-1089.
32. Uljaevna, U. F., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Development and education of preschool children. Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research

journal, 11(2), 326-329.

33. Shavkatovna, S. R. N. (2021). METHODOICAL SUPPORT OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Conferencea, 74-76.

34. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Conferencea, 97-102.

35. Oljayevna, O., & Shavkatovna, S. (2020). The Development of Logical Thinking of Primary School Students in Mathematics. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, 8(2), 235-239.

36. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Methodological Support for The Development of Primary School Students' Creative Activities. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 2, 121-123.

37. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(10), 289-292.

38. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 203-207.

39. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуллаева, С. (2022). ФИКРЛАШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МЕНТАЛ АРИФМЕТИКА. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 235-239.

40. Asqarov Anvarjon Rahimjon o‘g‘li. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING AQLIY TARAQQIYOTINING RIVOJLANISHIDA O‘YIN RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI FAOLIYAT SIFATIDA. Uzbek Scholar Journal, 5, 207–209.
41. Askarov, A. (2022). CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 87-91.
42. To‘lqinovna, Y. D. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MATEMATIK TASAVVURLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI. BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 25-31.
43. Yuldasheva Dilshoda To‘Lqinovna (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA BADIY TASVIRLAR ORQALI IZCHIL NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. Science and innovation, 1 (1), 741-750. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.653521
44. Yuldasheva, D. (2021). AGE AND THE SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 2(04), 124-130.
45. Tulkinovna, Y. D. (2021). On the Principle of Simple to Complex in the Development of Speech in Young Children. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 10, 32-35.
46. Ummatqulov, T. (2022). INSON SOG‘LOM BO‘LISHIDA VALEOLOGIYA FANINING AHAMIYATI. Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture, 2(12), 80-88.

47. SultonaliMannopov, A., AbdusalomSoliev, U., & TokhirShokirov, R. (2021). Development of Uzbek National Singing Art during Independence. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 6845-6853.

48. Rahmonov, U., Ergashev, A., Nazhmetdinova, M., & Usmonova, S. (2021, November). IN THE FORMATION OF THE SOCIO-SPIRITUAL THINKING OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE MUSICAL ART OF THE GREAT SCHOLARS OF THE EASTERN RENAISSANCE POSITION HELD. In Archive of Conferences (pp. 36-39).

Karimovich, U. R., Mamasodikovna, N. M., & Abdullaevich, E. A. (2021). The Role and Importance of Music Clubs in The Leisure of Young People. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices, 2(2), 47-49.

Rahmonov, U., Ergashev, A., Atabaeva, S., & Dilfuzakhon, S. Y. (2021, December). THE ROLE OF THE SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE PENETRATION OF POP MUSIC IN UZBEKISTAN. In Archive of Conferences (pp. 51-53).

Rahmonov, U., Ergashev, A., Atabaeva, S., & Dilfuzakhon, S. Y. (2021, December). THE ROLE OF THE SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE PENETRATION OF POP MUSIC IN UZBEKISTAN. In Archive of Conferences (pp. 51-53).

Ulugbek, R. (2021, January). AN ANALYSIS OF WORDS WHOSE EMOTIONAL MEANING CHANGES IN MODERN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. In Euro-Asia Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 131-136).

52. Qizi, G. S., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). The use of anthroponyms and pseudonyms in alisher Navoi's gazelles. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(9), 349-353.

53. Tillaboyeva, G., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). ALISHER NAVOIY ASARLARIDA BADIY TAXALLUSLARNING QO‘LLANILISHI. Студенческий вестник, (13-5), 70-72.

54. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). ALISHER NAVOIY SHE'RIYATIDA "SHAXS" TUSHUNCHASI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(2), 182-196.
55. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA LIBOS NOMLARI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 506-514.
56. Mohinur, D., & Rahimjon, U. (2022). A Study Of Memory Processes And Their Development In Preschool. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 62-65.
57. Rahim, U. (2021, May). SOCIAL FACTORS OF THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF MENTAL AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 25, No. 1, pp. 6-7).
58. Usmonov, R. (2022). O'SMIRLAR XULQIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK G'AYRATLILIK XUSUSIYATLARI TADQIQ ETISH METODOLOGIYASI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 127-135.
59. Usmonov, R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRI SHAXSIGA XOS ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDOSHUVLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 120-126.
60. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.
61. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.

62. Rakhmonovich, U. R. (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMONSTRATIVENESS, ENTHUSIASM AND AGGRESSIVENESS IN ADOLESCENCE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 820-824.

63. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 73-79.

64. Қурбонова, С. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЯНИ ЎҚИТИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ТАТБИҚ ЭТИШ. MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(17), 191-194.

65. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In *International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics* (pp. 512-513).

66. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). О ‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 39-44.

67. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). CHET EL OLIMLARI TOMONIDAN GURUHDAGI О ‘SMIRLAR VA AUTSAYDERLAR MUAMMOSINI О ‘RGANILISHNING OZIGA XOSLIGI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 33-38.

68. Noxida, D., & Saida, Q. (2022). TALABA QIZLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA TAYYORLASHNING ETNOPSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 309-314.

69. Dilshodbek O'g'li, R. S. (2022). The Role Of Physical Culture In Providing The Psychological Health Of The Athlete. Innovative Developments And Research In Education, Canada.

70. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH–IJTIMOIY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 30, 66-70.

71. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS. IJTIMOYIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 215-221.

72. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(11), 256-259.

73. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture, 2(12), 73-79.

74. Qurbonova, S. (2022). PSIXOLOGIYANI UQITIISHGA ZAMONAVIY PEDAOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARNI TATBIQ ETIISH. MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(17), 191-194.

75. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics (pp. 512-513).

76. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). O 'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 30, 39-44.

77. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). CHET EL OLIMLARI TOMONIDAN GURUHDAGI O ‘SMIRLAR VA AUTSAYDERLAR MUAMMOSINI O ‘RGANILISHNING OZIGA XOSLIGI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 33-38.

78 Noxida, D., & Saida, Q. (2022). TALABA QIZLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA TAYYORLASHNING ETNOPSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 309-314.

79. Kakharovna, A. M., Tadjimatovich, Y. M., Rakhmatovich, S. O., & Mirzahamdammovna, Q. B. (2021). Modern Approaches to the Teaching of Fine Arts. *Solid State Technology*, 64(2), 4250-4254.

80. Nazokat, A., Ibrokhim, Y., & Makhpuzakhon, A. (2021). FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF FINE ARTS.

81. M. Ahmedbekova (2022). ЁШ АВЛОДНИНГ БАДИИЙ-ЭСТЕТИК ИЖОДҚОРЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ТАСВИРИЙ САЊЪАТНИНГ ЖАМИЯТДАГИ ЎРНИ ВА АҲАМИЯТИ. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B8), 112-119. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7336303

Kipchakova, Y. (2021). METHODOLOGICAL AND DIDACTIC ASPECTS OF INFORMATION AND INTELLECTUAL CULTURE IN THE EDUCATION OF A DEVELOPED GENERATION. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1), 156-159.

Kipchakova, Y. X., & Kodirova, G. A. (2020). INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN EDUCATION. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (5), 29-31.

KIPCHAKOVA, Y., ABDUXAMIDOVA, M., & RAXMONALIYEVA, M. THE IMPACT OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING STUDENT KNOWLEDGE. *СТУДЕНЧЕСКИЙ ВЕСТНИК Учредители: Общество с ограниченной ответственностью "Интернаука"*, 37-38.

Қипчақова, Ё., Махмудова, М., & Умарова, З. (2021). МАКТАБГАЧА ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАР МЕҲНАТИНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТИ. *Студенческий вестник*, (22-7), 9-10.

Қипчақова, Ё., Соибжонова, Ш., & Абдуқаюмова, С. (2021). МАКТАБГАЧА

ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИДА СОҒЛОМ ТУРМУШ ТАРЗИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. Студенческий вестник, (22-7), 11-12.

Матмусаева, М. А. (2017). Оилада болаларни меҳнатга ўргатиш. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 23-24.

Матмусаева, М. А. (2019). ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ В РАЗВИТИИ ЧУВСТВА РОДИНЫ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ НА ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНЫХ И ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЯХ. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, (3-4), 103-106.

Матмусаева, М. А. (2016). ТАЛАБАЛАР ПОРТФОЛИОЛАРИНИ ТАЙЁРЛАШ ШАРОИТЛАРИ. In Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера (No. 9, pp. 129-131). Vedecko vydavatelske centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.

Матмусаева, М. А. (2016). ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ ЎҚУВ ФАОЛИЯТЛАРИНИ НАЗОРАТ ҚИЛИШНИНГ ИННОВАЦИОН ХАРАКТЕРИ. In Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера (No. 9, pp. 127-128). Vedecko vydavatelske centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.

Махамадалиевна, Y. D., & Matmusaeva, M. (2021). On Lingvofolcloristic Units. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 11, 169-171.

Матмусаева, М. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАСИ-МАКТАБГАЧА ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАР ИЖТИМОЙ ТАРБИЯ МАСКАНИ. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 2(20), 130-132.

Matmusayeva, M. A., & Rustamova, N. A. (2021). DEVELOPING LOGICAL THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. Theoretical & Applied Science, (6), 658-660.

Azamovna, M. M. PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN.

Nabijonova, F. (2022). Boshlangich sinflarda didaktik oyinlarning ahamiyati: Nabijonova Feruza. Qo'qon universitetining ilmiy materiallar bazasi, 1(000006).

Dilfuza, S., Nabijonova, F., & Matlubaxon, A. (2022). TA'LIM VA O'QITISH NAZARIYASINING MUHIM JIHATLARI. INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 2(19), 366-372.